

Disclaimer: This report is part of a project that has received funding by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement number 862568.

Jointly define a program for the CSS workshops on transition pathways (WP7)

Milestone number: 12

Milestone title: Jointly define a program for the CSS workshops on transition pathways

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Introduction

Aim: The aim of the workshops on transition pathways is to present the two visions for sustainable plant protection, to brainstorm what management at farm level would look like under each of these visions, and by applying the backcasting method, brainstorm on the building blocks for transition towards these two visions.

Moreover, SPRINT workshops also aim to facilitate exchange and mutual learning among the regional stakeholders on transition towards sustainable plant protection.

Who: Farmers, advisors, technical authorities, researchers, policy makers, breeders, biocontrol firms, civil society, retailers with a focus on progressive, open-minded and forward looking stakeholders who are committed to transition to reduced dependency on synthetic pesticides.

The aim is to have between 15 – 30 people participate in the workshop.

Try to make sure that all relevant stakeholders are represented. In best case scenario, you would have one or more stakeholders from each of the different types of groups listed above. One or two moderators/ facilitators from your team are needed. You can also ask a colleague from another group to facilitate the workshop – i.e. knowledge of content is not a prerequisite for facilitating.

When: As agreed with CSS leaders, the workshops will take place in February 2024.

Format and duration: as agreed in discussions with CSS leaders, the event can be structured as an in-person workshop or as a hybrid event. The duration is between 3 – 3.5hrs. We strongly recommend that you organise the event with different stakeholder groups at the same time. This will enable a fuller discussion among participants and more productive brainstorming, as different groups may think differently about different aspects of transition. However, if you decide to hold multiple smaller meetings due to the specific circumstances in your CSS, you should ensure that you cover the full scope of the questions asked.

Reporting: Reports of the workshops will be submitted no later than by the end of March 2024.

Invitations: Once you have identified a group of stakeholders that you would like to invite, you can adapt/translate the suggested invitation template with the agenda to either reach out

to stakeholders per Email or use other means of inviting them (by phone or in person) . To maximize the likelihood of people attending, we suggest to:

- Try to get people to hold a diary date from the earliest stage – this is also why it's important to set the date for the workshop as soon as possible
- Even when you send out an email invitation, use a personal approach as much as possible:
- Emails are functional but impersonal. If you use emails, try to personalize them and avoid blanket emails - i.e. always address them to a particular person
- A little flattery goes a long way – by adding a short line along the lines of 'you are essential to the process'
- If possible make personal contact, for example, by phone and then follow-up with an email
- Target the people that others respect: people are influenced by others, use this as a lever to get others attending

Dear >name of stakeholder<

We are pleased to invite you to the SPRINT workshop on transition to sustainable plant protection

The workshop will take place on >enter date< and location.

The workshop will focus on discussions around reducing reliance on synthetic pesticide use in >add your cropping system here>.

We will first present some initial findings on transition from earlier work conducted by the SPRINT project, and then discuss in smaller groups what pesticide reductions would look like in the cropping system and what kind of mix of support is needed to enable transition to reduced reliance on synthetic pesticides.

You can add here a short sentence why you think the stakeholder that you are inviting would be valuable participant (i.e. emphasize their importance for the workshop success).

The workshop agenda is attached to this email (or you can state that: 'the workshop agenda will be made available shortly').

Please let us know at your earliest convenience if you can attend the workshop.

We hope you will be able to join us at the workshop!

Kind regards,

Xxxx

Facilitator: The moderator is a facilitator of the mutual learning process. Her / his main tasks are:

- To create a relaxed and productive working atmosphere;
- To ensure the temporal and spatial organisation of the group's work;
- To foster an appreciative, respecting and accepting atmosphere within the group;
- To moderate the dialogue between participants;

What to avoid in the role of the facilitator?

- ... lecturing, teaching;
- ... dominating the process;
- ... judging the contributions of participants;
- ... emphasizing his or her own opinions and ideas concerning the thematic issues of the workshop.

Preparations and material required:

- The room should be set up in a world-café format, with 5-6 people at a table. If the numbers are lower, then 3-4 people at a table. If hybrid and your participant number is above 10, then we will need to discuss how to use break out groups (depending on whether you are using Teams or zoom software).
- You will need a flipchart for the room, and papers / pens and small paper cards (coloured) for each table
- Name tags if possible for people to wear, with name and organisation
- Introduction presentation – PPT will be provided in English by 20 January.
- Sticky dots of different colours for the ranking.

Programme for the workshops

08.45 -09.00	Arrival and coffee
09.00 – 09.30	Introduction, including brief presentation of most relevant results for your CSS (to be determined on an individual basis)
09.30 – 9.40	Participants introduce themselves around each table
09.40 - 10.10	Exercise 1: Small group discussion on the visions (incremental vs pesticide-free)
10.10 – 10.40	Exercise 2: Small group discussion on the building blocks for the two visions
10.40 – 11.55	Coffee break
11.55 – 12.25	Exercise 2: continuation
12.25 – 12.45	Exercise 3: Ranking of building blocks for transition and discussion.
12.45 – 13.00	Wrap up and next steps

Depending on your context, you can adjust the timing for the different blocks of the programme. For example, if you feel that you need more time for the discussion on the visions because the management options/pathways for farms need more discussion, then you could extend this for 10mins and reduce time for ranking.

If your meeting is hybrid or online, you can still use the same structure. However, we will assist you with preparing the Miro Board which you can use instead of flipcharts. It may also be possible to reduce the duration by 15mins or so.

A. Introduction

Objectives:

- To introduce the objectives and programme for the workshop (power point template prepared) – framing for the workshop.
- To “activate” and motivate participants, establish a relaxed working atmosphere. To give everybody an opportunity to present himself and his interest in the topic (“stake”)
- To set the mindset of ‘Yes, and ...’ and not ‘Yes, but ...’ → i.e. we want a positive mindset and open up imagination of what may be possible

Steps:

- The moderator welcomes participants.
- Introduce yourself, and briefly introduce SPRINT and workshop aims, as well as the workshop structure. Introduce briefly the ‘housekeeping rules’ – rules of the game

and conduct. Including that this is not a discussion about whether we need to reduce dependency on pesticide use. The focus is on how to do this with different degrees of ambition.

- This will be guided by a PPT template accompanied by notes that you will receive in January – the structure of the presentation will be:
 - Introduce concept of pesticide lock-in and briefly recap results from WS1 on barriers and solutions, and the D7.1 overview of barriers and solutions

Pesticide lock-in

- The alignment of mechanisms and barriers that drive stabilisation and status quo, restricting change.
- Lock-in is systemic because of strong interdependency and mutually-reinforcing mechanisms and barriers
- The technology (synthetic pesticides) is such a standard and dominant approach that change seems almost too costly and difficult

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- Introduce 2 visions (incremental 50% reduction and synthetic pesticide-free) and the purpose of 'thinking outside the box' exercise

- Highlight one or two success stories for synthetic pesticide-free vision (to be discussed individually with CSS leaders which story to focus on). This is to set a positive framing for discussions, to emphasize that we are thinking constructively of what is possible and would be needed, so that we don't get lost in barriers or 'this is not at all possible' or 'Yes, but...' mode of thinking.
- Introduce the concept of transition pathways for farms and the concept of a wider agri-food system transition based on three pillars: moving towards system re-design and accompanied by changes in food consumption and socio-economic relations. These are one possible way to move forward, but there may also be others.
- Emphasize that the focus is on opening up space for imagination. What we are looking for are solutions for plant protection and reducing reliance on synthetic pesticides that simultaneously also support biodiversity, climate goals and human well-being (farmers and society at large).

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Transition pathways towards reduced reliance on synthetic pesticides

Starting point

Vision 1
50% reduction in pesticide use and risk in 2030

Vision 2
Synthetic pesticide free agriculture in 2040

B. Exercise 1: Small group discussion on the visions (30 – 45mins, depending on the number of participants)

This discussion takes place in plenary.

Each table also has coloured paper for participants to write on.

- Your first refer to the management options for your cropping system, which had been collected from WP6 interviews with farm advisors and presented during the introduction. If your CSS did not conduct interviews with farm advisors, you prepare options based on your own knowledge or you conduct a couple of interviews with farm advisors / researchers in advance of the workshop yourself.
- Drawing on the Figure above (Transition pathways towards reduced reliance on synthetic pesticides): you present the management actions at farm level under the first three boxes (increased efficiency, substitution, and system re-design). In person, you would prepare these in advance on flipcharts and then add to the text already on flipcharts with posted-notes or coloured sheets of paper. In online/hybrid, these can be presented on the Miro Board (Ecologic Team will assist with this)
- These give ideas and options, but can be built on.
- Now tell participants that we are going to use a 'Time travel' imagination exercise. It may sound silly or unusual, but it is very real that one of the main barriers to move out of unsustainable state to more sustainable state is the lack of collective imagination of how things could be different. Which is why it is important to develop imagination and think outside the box.
- Brainstorm and validate with stakeholders what could management in your specific cropping system look like if we reduced reliance on synthetic pesticides by 50%?
 - What does a farm look like that relies much less on synthetic pesticides to manage pests, diseases, and weeds?
 - Participants are given time to discuss what might be missing or to add to the existing options any insights on feasibility or more nuance, or further details. You should also give the possibility that they write things down on posted-notes.
 - You can add the detail to the flipcharts on the wall.
- What would management look like for your case study and cropping system if we went to synthetic pesticide free agriculture in 2040? It's not utopia, it's what could be possible if everything that could possibly have been done was actually also done?
 - What does a future without reliance on synthetic pesticides look like at farm level for your specific case study? What kind of preventions elements and activities are in place? How does the farm day-to-day work look like? What does the space on the farm look like and feel like?

- What changes have been made to the whole system (what the farm producers, mix of crops and other elements, key elements such as fertilisation, also how the farm markets their produce, labour that they have available?. What could be put into place to focus on prevention and use of biocontrol options rather than synthetic pesticides?
- Thinking beyond existing examples of system re-design, what other options are imaginable?

Ask if anyone would like to hear more about a specific idea, and allow a minute or two for explanations. You can encourage more than one or two ideas to be explained, so that everyone has a good sense of the range of different ideas.

C. Exercise 2: Small group discussion how to achieve the two visions - ‘What if ...’

- To guide this discussion, keep in mind the key dimensions that shape current and future plant protection:
 - R&D and Knowledge
 - Economics
 - Policy
 - Regulation of pesticides (Authorisation etc)
 - Cognitive dimension
- Now, if we imagine that 50% reduction has been achieved, what would have happened to get there and then thinking further, if we imagine that we are nearly synthetic pesticide free, what would have happened to get there?
- At each table, participants can either focus on one or multiple dimensions, depending on what they feel most comfortable with. For each dimension, you can also use prompting to encourage discussion:
 - What conditions have changed for farmers? What kind of negotiating position do farmers have? What has changed to improve the price that they receive for their products?
 - What kind of knowledge has become available to better support farmers in reducing pesticide use? What was needed to make this knowledge available? What research projects were funded?
 - What does food consumption look like? How do consumers behave? What choices do the consumers have?
 - What movements and trends have inspired and informed the change in how we approach plant protection?
 - Etc...
 - The idea is to focus especially on the solutions: to elaborate and complement what is already available for your case study from the previous workshop and

interviews. And to also allow space for new ideas. You should emphasize that anything is possible here – imagination can run free ...

- Encourage participants to really think through a range of possible solutions. You can use inspiration from the success stories to encourage thinking and discussion.
- Participants use coloured post-it notes to add to the solutions and building blocks list.
- At the end of the discussion, you turn to the plenary. You use flipcharts that you put on the wall in the room and ask each table to put their respective coloured notes on the flipcharts. One flipchart for each dimension (economics... etc).
 - At the end of the session, you do a brief summary of what seem to be the key themes (just point to two or three most relevant themes)

D. Exercise 3: Ranking of options for transition

- To get sense of priorities, we would use the following method to do a ranking:
 - Each participant is given five sticky dots of one colour and they can allocate them to the solutions. One per solution or multiple ones for the same solution, depending on how strongly they feel about a particular solution.
 - Each participant is also given two 'veto' sticky dots (e.g. in red colour) which they can use for a solution that they really disagree on.
- At the end of this exercise, you do a brief recap of the results and you ask the participants if they would like to make any comments on the ranking outcomes.